

Review Article

Unipolar Versus Bipolar Depression. Clinical-Phenomenological Approach

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Abstract

The distinction between unipolar and bipolar depression remains one of the greatest clinical challenges in contemporary psychiatry. Despite manual descriptions (DSM, ICD) and validated criteria, many patients present in an ambiguous manner, with overlapping symptoms and clinical courses. This work, based on decades of clinical observations, seeks to phenomenologically delineate the typical profiles of individuals with unipolar depression and those with bipolar depression. It describes aspects of personality, lifestyle, relationship patterns, comorbidities, treatment response, and phenomenological manifestations of anxiety, using a broad clinical perspective grounded in direct comparisons.

Keywords: unipolar depression; bipolar depression; phenomenology; personality; anxiety; psychopathology

Introduction

Differentiating between unipolar major depressive disorder and bipolar disorder is critical for both clinical management and prognosis. Studies indicate that up to one-third of patients initially diagnosed with unipolar depression may, over time, be reclassified as bipolar (Perlis, 2006; McIntyre et al., 2017). However, long-term clinical observation often reveals nuances that go beyond standardized diagnostic criteria, allowing for a deeper understanding of the phenomenology of these conditions.

Phenomenology of Unipolar Individuals

According to reported clinical experience, patients with unipolar depression frequently present with a profile of shyness, social phobia, and genuine anxiety, often associated with asthenic or sthenic characteristics. These individuals tend to have high neuroticism, characterized by a rigid moral conscience, responsibility, and commitment to social and work obligations.

- **Unipolar Men:** are often alcoholics, drinking alone to relax or loosen up, generally shy, passive-aggressive, and often married to stronger or even older women. It is common for the women to be the ones who propose marriage.
- **Unipolar Women:** are frequently in stable professions (teachers, bank employees), with a disciplined life, neurotic, conscientious, and with little promiscuous sexual activity. Often, after an unsuccessful relationship, they remain in an enclosed, phobic, almost monastic life.

Unipolar individuals generally do not self-harm, do not exhibit "crazy" or impulsive behaviors, nor do they have episodes of sexual promiscuity. Their anxiety is described as a preoccupation and shyness anxiety, marked by insecurity, oppression, and fear, which is different from the impulsive anxiety of bipolar individuals. Psychopathologically, unipolar individuals do not "freak out" under normal conditions, except when faced with drugs or traumatic events, when they can develop reactive psychoses. They respond well to SSRI antidepressants, often need hypnotics for sleep, and have a more stable relationship with pharmacological treatment [Keller, 2006].

Phenomenology of Bipolar Individuals

In contrast, patients with bipolar depression present a distinct phenomenology. Their anxiety is marked by hyperactivity, emptiness, boredom, anguish, and impulsivity. They are more proactive, assertive individuals, often with a history of childhood hyperactivity (particularly women with ADHD). They differ from unipolar individuals in their search for excitement: sex, drugs, extreme sports, self-harm, sadomasochism, risky adventures, and promiscuous behaviors.

- **Bipolar Men:** tend to want to be bosses, leaders, in the spotlight, "moving the ball forward".
- **Bipolar Women:** have a frequent history of hyperactivity, academic instability, and multiple affective and sexual involvements, associated with intense impulsivity.

For treatment, they require mood stabilizers (lithium, valproate, carbamazepine), atypical antipsychotics, and in some cases, adjuvants like beta-blockers for autonomic symptoms. Bipolar individuals are highly vulnerable to the isolated use of antidepressants, which can precipitate mixed states, agitation, insomnia, and worsening of self-harm [Goodwin & Jamison, 2007].

Anxiety

Phenomenological Differentiation

A fundamental clinical point is the qualitative difference between unipolar and bipolar anxiety:

- **Unipolar:** anxiety of preoccupation, shyness, phobia, insecurity, fear, oppression.
- **Bipolar:** anxiety of boredom, agitation, emptiness, impulsivity, anguish without a defined object.

This phenomenological distinction has great heuristic value in clinical practice.

Life and Personality Profiles

- **Unipolar:** prefer the background, are conscientious, responsible, but oppressed by obligations. They prefer to be employees rather than bosses. Their sexual life is tamer and more disciplined. They tend to use alcoholism as a way to release stress.
- **Bipolar:** seek protagonism, the spotlight, entrepreneurship. They have greater assertiveness and impulsivity. Their sexual life is more promiscuous and they have a greater involvement with multiple drugs. They have a need for continuous stimulation.

Table 1: Clinical and Phenomenological Differences

Aspect	Unipolar	Bipolar
Personality	Shy, phobic, anxious, conscientious, passive-aggressive	Assertive, proactive, impulsive, seeks protagonism
Life History	Alcoholic men, women in stable professions, not very promiscuous	Entrepreneurial men, hyperactive and unstable women, promiscuous sexual life
Anxiety	Preoccupation, oppression, shyness, fear	Boredom, emptiness, impulsivity, anguish
Comorbidities	Alcoholism, phobias, anxiety	Drug use, self-harm, promiscuity
Evolution	Stable, rarely "freak out" (reactive psychoses)	Recurrent crises, mixed states, self-harm
Treatment	Effective SSRIs, hypnotics for sleep	Mood stabilizers, antipsychotics, risk of switching with antidepressants

Discussion

The clinical observations reported here are echoed in various studies that point to marked differences between unipolar and bipolar individuals in terms of age of onset, treatment response, comorbidities, and life trajectory [Angst et al., 2005; Perlis, 2006; McIntyre et al., 2017]. The originality of this work lies in offering a detailed phenomenological and psychodynamic reading, integrating personality characteristics, relational patterns, and anxiety, which do not appear clearly in diagnostic manuals but can assist the clinician in diagnostic differentiation.

Clinical Summary

Clinical Characteristics: Unipolar versus Bipolar

(Analysis from a Clinical Perspective)

Unipolar Depression

Individuals with unipolar depression are generally characterized as being shy, phobic, and anxious. They are often asthenic and, at the same time, sthenic, with a passive-aggressive personality. Among men, alcoholism is common, and they tend to marry women considered stronger or older. It is often the women who take the initiative to propose marriage. When it comes to women with unipolar depression, they often hold positions as teachers or bank employees, standing out for their great conscientiousness and high degree of neuroticism. The neuroticism index in these patients is, in fact, high. They are not "crazy" and do not fit the profile of people who self-harm, have impulsive acts of suicide, or are easily motivated. They are more stable and are generally responsible.

The worsening of the condition, which can manifest as an increase in anxiety or a deepening of depression, is usually triggered by a biological, psychological, social, or professional event. The family history of these patients does not usually have records of bipolar disorder or "crazy" behaviours. On the contrary, they are quite conscientious. While some may develop alcoholism, they do not usually resort to other drugs or self-harm, as is the case with bipolar individuals. There is no history of sexual promiscuity in these individuals. Unlike bipolar type 2 individuals, they are not hyperactive. They are more phobic and anxious.

Bipolar Disorder

Individuals with bipolar disorder, when medicated with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, tend to have noradrenergic reactions. This can lead to irritation, akathisia, insomnia, excess negative energy, mixed states, or worsening of self-harm and suicide risk. The clinical history of bipolar individuals, especially in women, frequently includes hyperactivity with attention deficit, which may have led to academic difficulties. They have a common history of hyperactivity. Additionally, sexual promiscuity is more frequent among them, and men may be the ones who harass women. Women, in turn, may have a more promiscuous life. Bipolar individuals are always "moving forward," focused on the future. They are proactive, assertive, and tend to want to be bosses, build, and stand out. They seek the spotlight, the evidence. It is common for bipolar individuals to have feelings of boredom and existential emptiness. They crave dopamine, seeking extreme sports, great adventures, sex, drugs, and rock'n'roll. They may also manifest self-harm, cuts, masochism, and sadism. Their energy is more disorganized, and the anxiety they feel is different from unipolar anxiety.

Comparisons and Treatment Responses

Psychological and Behavioral Manifestations

Unipolar individuals tend to feel oppressed and suffocated, often needing medication to sleep. However, they do not have suicidal impulsivity. Their anxiety is seen as more "genuine," manifesting as preoccupation, oppression, fear, shyness, phobia, and insecurity. They are very conscientious, committed, and dependent on others, and tend to be more reserved, preferring the background. In contrast, the anxiety of bipolar individuals is more hyperactive, derived from boredom and emptiness. It is an anxiety of "no way out," of agony, anguish, and impulsivity. They may exhibit more psychopathic, cold behavior with an "I don't care" attitude. Unlike unipolar individuals, they can have "outbursts" of aggression.

Treatment Response

Unipolar individuals tend to respond well to selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors. Bipolar individuals, on the other hand, need mood stabilizers, such as lithium, valproate, or carbamazepine, in addition to neuroleptics and antipsychotics. In many cases, psychostimulants or medications for hyperactivity, such as propranolol, are also necessary.

Professional and Social Life

Unipolar individuals, in the case of men, may feel oppressed by obligations. They often do not like to work because of the pressure from their boss. However, they work because they are conscientious and responsible, even if it is a heavy burden. They prefer to be employees rather than bosses and like more free and light activities. On the other hand, bipolar individuals have a proactivity and assertiveness that lead them to want to be bosses and to be in the spotlight. Unipolar individuals rarely have "outbursts," unless they are provoked by drugs or other factors, such as reactive or psychogenic psychoses. Bipolar individuals, as mentioned, are prone to crises of aggression. Bipolar individuals have a common history of hyperactivity, even in women, who may have academic difficulties due to attention deficit. Unipolar individuals are generally more timid in the sexual area and, in the case of men, are often harassed. If a relationship does not work out for unipolar women, they may become reclusive and even lead a "nun's" life, avoiding new relationships.

Conclusion

The distinction between unipolar and bipolar depression goes beyond traditional nosology. While unipolar individuals tend to have more disciplined, anxious, conscientious, and phobic life profiles, bipolar individuals present with impulsive energy, a higher risk of self-harm, promiscuity, and a search for excitement. The phenomenology of anxiety, in particular, constitutes a key element for this differentiation.

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